

Light-Weight Time-Packing Detection Schemes for Optical Feeder Link Adaptation in High Throughput Satellite Systems

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Abstract—This paper shows low complex decoding algorithms for time-packed optical feeder links when they are used in High Throughput Satellite (HTS) system with fully regenerative payloads. Time-packed M -ary Pulse Amplitude Modulation (M -PAM) is used to modulate the intensity of the laser diode beam by means of an external Mach-Zehnder modulator. At the receiver, the symbols are detected by resorting to a photodetector, encapsulated into the 5G radio frame of the access link, and demodulated using the Viterbi Algorithm (VA). However, if the modulation order and/or the overlapping factor are high and/or the roll-off factor of the pulse-shape is low, then the number of Viterbi states can be too high. Towards this regard, we have studied the mitigation capability of Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) equalizer and transversal filter adapted by Least-Mean Squares (LMS) algorithm. As expected, both techniques, although sub-optimal, permit to mitigate in a large extent the Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) and so, provide a finer granularity on the link adaptation of the optical feeder link.

Index Terms—High throughput satellite; optical feeder link; regenerative payload; link adaptation; adaptive equalization; time-packing.

I. INTRODUCTION

High Throughput Satellite (HTS) systems evolve from offering broadcasting to 5G data services in remote areas of the globe as well as in emergency applications [1]. In order to provide an aggregate data rate of few Terabit-per-second (Tbps), GEO satellites had to utilize a very large number of spot-beams with an aggressive frequency reuse factor in the radio *access link* (*i.e.*, from the satellite to the user terminals) [2], and possibly optical wireless technology to support a similar point-to-point data rate on the *feeder link* (*i.e.*, from the gateway to the satellite) [3]. Specifically, *real-valued* modulation can be used to transport the payload bits on the optical feeder link, which is compatible with an Intensity Modulation (IM)/Direct Detection (DD) implementation. Unfortunately, real-valued modulations such as M -PAM are used in the IM/DD optical feeder link, have limited degrees-of-freedom for link adaptation, as the BER of M -PAM grows notably when $M \gg 2$. Therefore, if time-packing is added on top of the adaptive modulation scheme, the

overlapping factor of the M -PAM signal can be used as an additional parameter to adapt the spectral efficiency of the optical feeder link. In order to overcome this drawback, this paper proposes to use Faster-Than-Nyquist strategy.

Faster-than-Nyquist signaling, also known as *time-packing*, was proposed as a technique to increase the spectral efficiency of a communication channel [4] with augmenting the required bandwidth. More precisely, it was shown that in presence of a binary sequence of *Sinc*-pulses, a 25%-data-rate-increase is achievable by shrinking the time between adjacent *Sinc*-pulses to about 80.2% of the Nyquist symbol time. Unfortunately, the complexity of the receiver grows notably when the rolloff factor decreases and/or the overlapping factor between pulses increases and/or modulation augments [5], [6]. For that reason is necessary to look for light-weight architectures that be able of decoding time-packing in these cases [7].

In this paper, we focus on the removal of the ISI that introduces the time-packed signal using shortened Viterbi and MMSE equalizers as well as a LMS-transversal filter. Different design parameters are considered in the performance evaluation, such as the overlapping factor and the modulation. The roll-off factor of the Square-Root Raised-Cosine (SRRC) filters and the number of states of the Viterbi's Trellis have been kept constant to $\rho = 0.15$, and $N_s = 4096$ respectively. As expected, the use of LMS-transversal filter for decoding time-packing provides additional degrees-of-freedom to implement the adaptation of the optical feeder link, enabling a higher spectral efficiency than the one obtained when using adaptive modulation solely.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the principles of time-packing and the details of the ML, MMSE and LMS-transversal equalizers. Section IV introduces the most important blocks of the optical feeder link, including the IM transmitter, the optical wireless channel, and the DD receiver. The details of the simulation setup, as well as the evaluation of adaptive modulation with time-packing signaling are presented in Section V. Finally, Section VI draws the main conclusions of the paper.

II. TIME-PACKING: PRINCIPLES AND DETECTION SCHEMES

This section summarizes the key time-packing theoretical principles as well as the detection schemes for recovering

This work has received funding from the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities of Spain under project TERESA-TEC2017-90093-C3-1-R (AEI/FEDER,UE) and from the Catalan Government under Grants 2017-SGR-00891 and 2017-SGR-01479.

the transmitted symbols in an optimal and a sub-optimal way by resorting to ML and light-weight decoding schemes respectively. At this point, it is necessary to remark that the time-packed strategy is applied to the real-valued modulation scheme of the IM/DD optical feeder link.

A. Principle of time-packing

The time-packed signal in the time-domain that the transmitter generates can be formulated as

$$s(t) = \sum_k s[k] g_{\text{tx}}[t - k(1 - \delta)T_s], \quad (1)$$

being k the position of the data symbol in the input stream $\{s[k] : k = 1, \dots\}$, T_s represents the Nyquist symbol time, $g_{\text{tx}}(t)$ symbolizes the time response of the transmit pulse-shaping filter, and δ indicates the overlapping factor used for time-packing. The transmit pulses with response $g_{\text{tx}}(t)$ have unit energy and are orthogonal when shifted by integer multiples of T_s . Nevertheless, in time-packing the orthogonality among pulses is lost as $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_{\text{tx}}(t)g_{\text{tx}}(t - n(1 - \delta)T_s)dt \neq 0$ holds. Therefore, it is added an Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) signal but in return, an increase in the time signaling rate $R'_s = R_s/(1 - \delta) \geq R_s = 1/T_s$ can be achieved without increasing the communication bandwidth. In short, time-packing permits a more efficient use of the communication bandwidth at the expenses of adding ISI, which should be mitigated adding complexity in reception.

Let us consider that the continuous-time received signal is $r(t) = s(t) + n(t)$, where $n(t)$ is Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). Then, the sufficient statistics for symbol detection can be obtained after applying Match Filtering (MF) [8], *i.e.*,

$$\begin{aligned} r[n] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r(t) g_{\text{rx}}(t - n(1 - \delta)T_s) dt \\ &= \sum_k s[k] c[k - n] + \eta[n], \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $g_{\text{rx}}(t) = g_{\text{tx}}(-t)^*$ and, for that reason,

$$c[k - n] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_{\text{tx}}(t - k(1 - \delta)T_s) g_{\text{tx}}(-t + n(1 - \delta)T_s)^* dt, \quad (3)$$

$$\eta[n] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} n(t) g_{\text{tx}}(-t + n(1 - \delta)T_s)^* dt, \quad (4)$$

which is the so-called Ungerboeck observation model [9]. Unfortunately, this model is not practical since the ISI in (2) is non-causal and the noise samples $\eta[n]$ are correlated. In order to avoid these problems, the signal after MF is passed through a whitening filter [10]. By doing so, we obtain

$$r'[n] = \sum_k s[k] c'[k - n] + \eta'[n], \quad (5)$$

being $c'[k]$ for $k \neq n$ the causal ISI verifying that $c'[k] * c'[-k]^* = c[k]$, and $\eta'[n]$ are AWGN samples. Note that the time-duration and magnitude of this ISI will depend on the used modulation, roll-off and overlapping factors. Next, (5) can be expressed in matrix form as:

$$\mathbf{r}' = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s} + \boldsymbol{\eta}', \quad (6)$$

Thus, if L_c symbolizes the number of delay samples after the matched filter and M the number of modulated symbols then, $\mathbf{r}' \in \mathbb{R}^{M+L_c \times 1}$ is the vector that stacks the received time-packed samples, *i.e.* $\mathbf{r}' = [r'[-(L_c+1)/2], r'[n], r'[M+(L_c-1)/2]]^T$, $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{R}^{M+(L_c-1)/2 \times 1}$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}' \in \mathbb{R}^{M+L_c \times 1}$ are the vectors of the transmitted information symbols and noise samples respectively. The symbol \mathbf{H} , represents the channel convolution matrix, $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{M+L_c \times M+(L_c-1)/2}$, and has the following structure, including initial and final transition states,

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} c'[k] & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c'[k] & \dots & c'[k - L_c] & \dots \\ 0 & c'[k] & \dots & c'[k - L_c] \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & c'[k] & \dots & c'[k - L_c] \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & c'[k] \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

After presenting the generation of the time-packing signal and its properties, next section shows strategies for detecting the transmitted symbols.

B. Detection Schemes

This section presents the Maximum Likelihood (ML) sequence estimator which it is the optimal strategy in terms of BER for decoding the transmitted time-packed symbols and two sub-optimal ones: Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) equalization and Least Mean Squares (LMS) transversal filter.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

1) *Optimum Detection: ML detector:* The ML estimation of sequence $\mathbf{s} = \{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_{N-1}\}$ based on the received signal samples $r[n]$ maximizes the next cost function

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{s}} f(r[n]|\mathbf{s}), \quad (8)$$

being $f(r[n]|\mathbf{s})$ the conditional Probability Density Function (PDF) of the received signal samples $\{r[n] : n = 0, \dots, N - 1\}$ when \mathbf{s} has been transmitted. Then, when it is used M -PAM modulation, then ML detector needs to compute M^N trial sequences. So, it turns the computational complexity of the detector to grow as $\mathcal{O}(M^N)$.

This notable load can be notably reduced with the aid of the Viterbi algorithm [8], which takes advantage of the trellis structure of the overall communication channel (including the SRRC filters). Thus, the implementation complexity reduces from $\mathcal{O}(M^N)$ to $\mathcal{O}(M^{L_T})$, where L_T is the channel memory. Fortunately, in time-packing the overall channel memory is a design parameter that can be controlled using channel shortening techniques [11], by augmenting the roll-off factor of the SRRC filters, and decreasing the overlapping factor [10].

Fig. 1: Block schemes of the ML, MMSE and LMS-transversal filters

By doing so, the PAPR in transmission and the energy consumption in reception are reduced but, in return, the spectral efficiency of the communication channel may be impacted if the BER due to residual ISI grows [12]. Studying these figures, it is possible to conclude that the number of channel coefficients introduces notable ISI that grows with the order of the M -PAM modulation [7]. Nevertheless, our goal consists on only considering only part of the time-packing ISI in the ML decoding. For that reason, there will be some residual ISI that will make the received Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio

$$\text{SINR} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|s[n]|^2\} c'[0]^2}{\mathbb{E}\{|s[n]|^2\} \sum_{k=L_T}^{\infty} |c'[k]|^2 + N_0}, \quad (9)$$

where L_T is the number of ISI symbols that Viterbi Algorithm takes into account, N_0 symbolizes the noise power, and $\mathbb{E}\{s[n]\}$ represents the mathematical expectation of $s[n]$. By replacing the SNR with the SINR, the closed formula for the error probability of the k -th bit of the M -PAM symbol will be [13]:

$$P_b[k] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{l=0}^{(M-1)-M2^{-k}} \left\{ (-1)^{\lfloor \frac{l2^{k-1}}{M} \rfloor} \left(2^{l-1} - \left[\frac{l2^{k-1}}{M} + \frac{1}{2} \right] \right) \text{erfc} \left((2l+1) \sqrt{\frac{3 \text{SINR}}{(M^2-1)}} \right) \right\} \quad (10)$$

where $\lfloor x \rfloor$ is the largest integer less than or equal to x and $\text{erfc}(x) = 1/\sqrt{2\pi} \int_x^{\infty} \exp(-t^2) dt$ represents the complementary error function. Thus, the BER for M -PAM will be,

$$\text{BER}(M) = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{P_b[k]}{m}, \quad m = \log_2(M). \quad (11)$$

Based on the previous formulas, the feasible throughput becomes

$$\text{TH}(\rho, \delta) = W \frac{(1 - \text{BLER}) \log_2(M) R_c}{(1 - \delta)(1 + \rho)}, \quad W = \frac{1}{2T_s}, \quad (12)$$

where the Block Length Error Rate (BLER) is calculated encapsulating L_p bits per data packet, i.e., $\text{BLER} = 1 - (1 - \text{BER})^{L_p}$, and the error control coding rate $R_c = 1$ for simplicity (uncoded case).

2) *Sub-optimum Detection: Minimum Mean Square Error:* The estimates provided by the MMSE equalizer are obtained by performing the following linear processing

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{A}_{MMSE}^T \mathbf{r}', \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_{MMSE} \in \mathbb{R}^{M+L_c \times M+(L_c-1)/2}$ accounts for the equalization matrix. The design of matrix \mathbf{A}_{MMSE} is governed by the MMSE criterion, namely

$$\zeta_{MMSE} = \min_{\mathbf{A}_{MMSE}} \mathbf{E} \{ \mathbf{e}^T \mathbf{e} \}. \quad (14)$$

with $\mathbf{e} = \hat{\mathbf{s}} - \mathbf{s}$. Since the objective function is convex, \mathbf{A}_{MMSE} is obtained by setting the partial derivatives equal to zero [14]. Then, we end-up with this closed-form expression

$$\mathbf{A}_{MMSE} = \left(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^T + \frac{\mathbf{R}_{\eta'}}{E_s} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{H}, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbb{E} \{ \boldsymbol{\eta}' \boldsymbol{\eta}'^T \} = \mathbf{R}_{\eta'}$ is the correlation matrix of the noise plus residual co-channel interference term and E_s is the mean energy symbol. To get (15) it has been assumed that symbols are statistically independent, i.e. $\mathbb{E} \{ s_q[n] s_m^*[l] \} = E_s \delta_{q,m} \delta_{n,l}$.

3) *Sub-optimum Detection: Least Mean Square transversal filter:* In the previous strategy, the estimated symbols are obtained from the product between the MMSE equalization matrix, \mathbf{A}_{MMSE} , (See (15)) and the received data, \mathbf{r}' . On the contrary, in the transversal filter, the estimation of the current symbol is computed as:

$$\hat{s}[n] = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{y}[n], \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the vector that stacks the L_w weights of the filter, $\mathbf{w} = [w[0], \dots, w[L_w - 1]]^T$ and \mathbf{y}_j is the vector that stacks the $(L_w - 1)/2$ a priori and posteriori received samples to the symbol to estimate, i.e. $\mathbf{y}[n] = [r'[n - (L_w - 1)/2], \dots, r'[n], \dots, r'[n + (L_w - 1)/2]]^T$. However, in this case, the weights of this equalizer are not calculated from any closed-expression. They come from using the LMS adaptive strategy and a set of training sequences. By doing so, the updating process of the transversal filter weights for the j -th Monte-Carlo training sequence at the n -th training symbol is [15]:

$$\mathbf{w}_j[n] = \mathbf{w}_j[n-1] + \mu e_j[n] \mathbf{y}_j[n], \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_j[n] \in \mathbb{R}^{L_w \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{w}_j[n-1] \in \mathbb{R}^{L_w \times 1}$ represent the vector of L_w coefficients of the transversal filter at the current and previous training iteration, i.e. $\mathbf{w}_j = [w_j[0], \dots, w_j[L_w - 1]]^T$, μ is the forgetting parameter of the LMS algorithm which is ranged between $0 < \mu < 1/\lambda_{max}$, being λ_{max} the maximum eigenvalue of the received data correlation matrix, i.e., $R = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{y}^T\}$, $e_j[n]$ is the error from the current estimated symbol and the training one, denoted as $\hat{s}_j[n]$ and $s_j[n]$ respectively, being equated as: $e_j[n] = s_j[n] - \hat{s}_j[n]$. Towards this regards, if the j -th training sequence, \mathbf{s}_j spans L_T symbols, and the reference coefficients are taken from the last training sample, i.e. $\mathbf{w}_j[L_T]$, then it can be decomposed as:

$$\mathbf{w}_j[L_T] = \mathbf{w}_o + \sigma_{T,j} \xi_j, \quad (18)$$

being $\mathbf{w}_o \in \mathbb{R}^{L_w \times 1}$ the optimal L_w training coefficients, which would provide the MMSE solution. Regarding $\xi_j \in \mathbb{R}^{L_w \times 1}$, it represents the Gaussian noise of zero mean and power $\sigma_{T,j}^2$ that shifts the reference coefficients from the optimal ones. Next, if there were P Monte-carlo trials for selecting the optimal coefficients of the transversal filter, denoted as \mathbf{w} , and the noise power error in their estimation $\sigma_{T,j}^2$ was identical for all training sequences, i.e. $\sigma_{T,1}^2 = \dots = \sigma_{T,P}^2 = \sigma_T^2$, then the optimal coefficients \mathbf{w} would be:

$$\mathbf{w} = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{j=0}^{P-1} \mathbf{w}_j[L_T] = \mathbf{w}_o + \frac{\sigma_T}{P} \boldsymbol{\varsigma}, \quad (19)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varsigma}$ is Gaussian noise of zero mean and deviation σ_T/P . Finally after proving the theoretical principles on time-packing, its optimal detection and light-weight sequence detection, we are now ready to study the performance when IM/DD optical feeder links use time-packet M -PAM encoding.

IV. OPTICAL FEEDER LINK WITH TIME-PACKING

A. Optical wireless channel modeling

In an optical feeder link the Free Space Loss (FSL) is the largest power loss, and it is computed as

$$L_{o,fsl} = \lambda^2 / (4\pi d_{fso})^2, \quad (20)$$

being d_{fso} the range and λ symbolizes the wavelength of the optical feeder links. Additional losses are the ones produced by atmospheric conditions such as the weather ones in which visibility is reduced. It is important to note that the range of atmospheric losses, $L_{o,atm}$, can be so low as a few dBs for *Fog* and *Cirriform clouds*, few tens of dBs in case of *Stratocumulus* and *Altostratus*, and from few hundreds to few thousand dBs in presence of *Cumulonimbus*. For cloudy weather, $L_{o,atm}$, will depend on the thickness and density of water droplets that clouds contain [16]. Although, wireless optical communication are not possible in presence of heavy *Cumulonimbus*, our aim it to use time-packing as enabler of better link adaptation granularity, such that the throughput of the optical feeder link is optimized assuming partly cloudy weather in which $L_{o,atm}$ is few tens of dBs.

Finally, the *atmospheric turbulence* is generated by mixing warm and cold air on the different layers of the atmosphere. To

TABLE I: Parameters of the optical feeder link of the HTS system.

Symbol	Optical Link Parameter	Value	Unit
$P_{o,ld}$	Average optical power of Laser Diode	47.0	dBm
$G_{o,tx}$	Optical gain of transmitter (ground telescope)	112.2	dB
$G_{o,rx}$	Optical gain of receiver (satellite telescope)	114.1	dB
$L_{o,fsl}$	FSL of optical link (1550 nm, 39000 km)	290.0	dB
$L_{o,atm}$	Atmospheric loss due to thin cloud layers	0 – 20	dB
$L_{o,sys}$	System losses in the optical feeder link	4.7	dB
G_{edfa}	Gain of the optical amplifier (EDFA)	50.0	dB
μ	Responsivity of photodetector (PIN diode)	0.5	A/W
B_e	Bandwidth of electrical filter (PD output)	1.5	GHz
B_o	Bandwidth of optical channel (1550 nm)	12.5	GHz
ρ_{ase}	PSD of amplified spontaneous emissions	2.0×10^{-19}	W/Hz
ρ_{rin}	PSD of RIN process (normalized)	-160	dBc/Hz
ρ_{back}	PSD of background noise at EDFA input	7.6×10^{-25}	W/Hz
i_n	Electrical noise current spectral density	1.0×10^{-11}	A
i_{dark}	Dark current at the PIN diode output	1.0×10^{-10}	A

reduce the effect of this impairment, a few dBs of the optical feeder link budget are reserved as *system losses* to include the atmospheric losses produced by turbulences.

B. Direct Detection of the optical signal on board the satellite

The electrical current from the illumination on the Photo Detector (PD) is expressed as:

$$i_D(t) = I_D + i_d(t) = \mu \frac{G_{o,tx} G_{o,rx} G_{o,edfa}}{L_{o,fsl} L_{o,atm} L_{o,sys}} \int_t^{t+T_o} p_o(\tau) d\tau, \quad (21)$$

$$\int_t^{t+T_o} p_o(\tau) d\tau = \frac{P_{o,ld}}{2} \left[1 + \sin(\beta \tilde{s}(t)) \right] \quad (22)$$

being $T_o = 2\pi/\omega_o$ the period of the optical carrier, μ [A/W] represents the PD responsivity, $G_{o,tx}$ and $G_{o,rx}$ are the optical gains of the transmit and receive telescopes, respectively, $G_{o,edfa}$ is the gain of the Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA), and $L_{o,sys}$ encompasses the system losses in the optical feeder link. Note that the current in (21) can be decomposed into two terms, where the DC component is given by

$$I_D = \mathbb{E}\{i_D(t)\} = \mu \frac{G_{o,tx} G_{o,rx} G_{o,edfa}}{L_{o,fsl} L_{o,atm} L_{o,sys}} \frac{P_{o,ld}}{2}, \quad (23)$$

and keeps fixed regardless of β , whereas the AC component depends on the intensity modulation index and attains the form

$$i_d(t) = i_D(t) - I_D = I_D \sin(\beta \tilde{s}(t)) \approx I_D \beta \tilde{s}(t) \quad \beta \ll 1. \quad (24)$$

Thus, the SNR of the electrical signal that is direct-detected by the PD on-board the GEO satellite is

$$\text{SNR}_{e,pd} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|i_d(t)|^2\}}{\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}} \approx \frac{I_D^2 \beta^2}{\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}} \quad \beta \ll 1, \quad (25)$$

where the noise power $\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}$ is the sum of multiple independent sources of noise:

$$\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{|i_{shot}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{thermal}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{rin}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{beat}(t)|^2\}, \quad (26)$$

which are: *shot noise*, *thermal noise*, *Relative Intensity Noise* (RIN) of LD, and *beat noise* [17]. Take into account that shot noise term includes the contribution of the received optical signal, the Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE)

noise, background optical noise and the dark current noise, whereas the beat noise term includes the effect of combining the received optical signal with the ASE noise. If the received optical power is ranged between -90 and -20 dBW, then the beat noise between received optical signal and ASE noise dominates the SNR performance of the optical feeder link [18]. In this case, we have that

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\} &\approx \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{beat}}(t)|^2\} = i_{\text{sig-sp}}^2 + i_{\text{sp-sp}}^2 \\ &\approx i_{\text{sig-sp}}^2 = 4 I_D I_{\text{ase}} (B_e/B_o),\end{aligned}\quad (27)$$

where B_o and B_e are the bandwidth of the optical signal and the electrical signal at the input and output of the PD, respectively, whereas $I_{\text{ase}} = \mu G_{\text{o,edfa}} P_{\text{ase}}$ is the DC component caused by the ASE noise when $P_{\text{ase}} = \rho_{\text{ase}} B_o$ is the equivalent noise power of the EDFA before amplification.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Table I summarizes the parameters of the optical feeder link, taking into account both the optical gains and optical losses [19], and the different sources of optical noise [18]. The effect of any other parameter not listed in this table will be considered in this paper as negligible (*e.g.*, specific PD non-idealities and optical wireless channel impairments).

According to these values, the mean received optical power is

$$\begin{aligned}P_{\text{o,rx}}[\text{dBm}] &= P_{\text{o,ld}}[\text{dBm}] + G_{\text{o,tx}}[\text{dB}] + G_{\text{o,rx}}[\text{dB}] - L_{\text{o,fsl}}[\text{dB}] \\ &\quad - L_{\text{o,sys}}[\text{dB}] - L_{\text{o,atm}}[\text{dB}] = -21.4[\text{dBm}] - L_{\text{o,atm}}[\text{dB}].\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

In case of clear-sky conditions (*i.e.*, when $L_{\text{o,atm}} = 0$ dB), the DC current obtained by the optical signal at the output of the PD is $I_D = 181.11$ mA, whereas the DC current generated by the ASE noise is $I_{\text{ase}} = 0.125$ mA regardless the weather. Thus, if the intensity modulation index $\beta = 0.5$, the SNR of the electrical signal at the output of the PD becomes

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{e,pd}}[\text{dB}] = 28.78[\text{dB}] - L_{\text{o,atm}}[\text{dB}].\quad (29)$$

Greater intensity modulation indexes β could be used without augmenting the MZM non-linear distortion notably. However, Digital Pre-Distortion compensation would have to be implemented in transmission [17]. In any case, in this paper we assume that the MZM works on its linear region due to the input signal is set low enough most of the time. Fig. 2 shows the BER as function of the received SINR for the $M \in \{2,4,8\}$ -PAM modulation schemes respectively, roll-off factor $\rho = 0.15$, overlapping factor $\delta \in \{15, 25, 40\}\%$ and ML, MMSE and LMS decoding strategies. In the ML decoder has been used a Trellis of $N_s = 4096$ states (demanding Trellis) for all M -PAM modulations. The LMS filter uses $P=10$ training sequences that span 10000 symbols and 7 coefficients for all modulations. The MMSE equalizer uses 7 coefficients for 2-PAM, 11 for 4-PAM and 21 for 8-PAM. Fig. 2a shows BER of these receivers for 2-PAM. There it is possible to see that for all overlapping factors the MLSE detector always attains the BER in absence of ISI, *i.e.* $\delta = 0\%$. The LMS adapted transversal filter provides similar BER for all δ but approximately 1 dB larger in SINR than the ML detector for

getting the same BER. Finally, for the MMSE equalizer, it provides an error floor for all overlapping factors since the truncation of the channel matrix impacts on the estimation of its weights. This conclusion keeps for all modulations. Fig. 2b represent the BER in terms of the receiver SINR for the 4-PAM modulation. Results show that MLSE equalizer would require a larger number of states to fit the BER in absence of ISI at larger overlapping factors, *i.e.* $\delta \in \{25\%, 40\%\}$. However, there is no error floor for any overlapping factor when it is used MLSE equalizer. Regarding the LMS-transversal filter, it provides similar BER than MLSE for an overlapping factor of $\delta = 25\%$ and a much better performance for $\delta = 40\%$. Fig. 2c plots the BER for the 8-PAM modulation. From this figure is possible to conclude that only the LMS transversal filter is able to follow the BER in absence of ISI. The other two detectors have an error floor at high SINRs. The complexity constraint of the MLSE detector limits notably its performance. This is because the number of states used in the Trellis are not enough to remove the ISI generated by few adjacent symbols (*i.e.*, short channel memory). As a result, the residual ISI is important, and the BER performance increases notably.

Finally, Fig. 3 plots the normalized throughput as function of the cloud attenuation that M -PAM with time-packing achieves for the ML, MMSE and LMS decoders. The roll-off factor is $\rho = 0.15$ and three different overlapping factors are studied: $\delta = 0$ (no overlapping), $\delta = 0.15$ (low overlapping), and $\delta = 0.4$ (large overlapping). The number of bits that are encapsulated per data packet is $L_p = 2536$. This packet length corresponds to the maximum Transport Block Size (TBS) from the PUSCH of NB-IoT radio technology standard [20]. The target BER is 10^{-4} . From these figures, it is possible to observe that for ML-decoding time-packing decoding is always the best selection except when the attenuation is between 17-18 dB and 10.5-11 dB. For MMSE equalization Nyquist signaling is always the best option except for a cloud attenuation ranged between 11-18.5 dB. Finally for the LMS transversal filter time-packing modulation is always the best choice.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper was studied three possible light-weight time-packing architectures: shortened MLSE and MMSE equalizers, and LMS transversal filter as well as their achievable throughput. The modulation of the intensity of the optical feeder link in a HTS system with fully-regenerative payload is a time-packed M -PAM. The ISI that the time-packing modulation adds can be partially removed by the Trellis constrained ML decoder and LMS transversal filter in a large extent although the last one presents a better performance when the modulation order increases. On the other hand, the shortened MMSE presents an error floor from 4-MAP which limits its performance. From these results, it is possible to assess that M -PAM using time-packing and LMS transversal filtering can be a good alternative for increasing the data rate in IM/DD optical links without increasing data bandwidth. In this configuration are used real-valued modulations which limits notably

Fig. 2: BER as function of the electrical SINR for different optical feeder link configurations when the rolloff is $\rho = 0.15$. Modulation: 2-PAM, 4-PAM, and 8-PAM. Overlapping factors: $\delta = 0$ (solid lines), $\delta = 0.15$ (dashed lines with circles), $\delta = 0.25$ (dashed lines with squares) and $\delta = 0.4$. Trellis states in Viterbi Algorithm: $N_s = 4096$ for 2,4 and 8-PAM

Fig. 3: Normalized throughput of the IM/DD optical feeder link in terms of the cloud losses when using time-packed M -PAM with ($\rho = 0.15$, $N_s = 4096$ states, $L_p = 2536$ bits, Target $BER = 10^{-4}$). Modulation: 2-PAM (red lines), 4-PAM (green lines), 8-PAM (blue lines). Overlapping factor: $\delta = 0$ (solid lines), $\delta = 0.15$ (dashed-lines with circles), $\delta = 0.4$ (dashed-lines with squares). Fig. 3a ML decoder, Fig. 3b MMSE equalizer and Fig. 3c LMS filter

the possible transmission schemes. By doing so, the slowly-varying attenuation that thin cloud layers introduce can be solved by modifying the cardinality of the modulation M and the overlapping factor δ of the time-packed signal that modulates the intensity of the optical feeder link. Consequently, it is possible to conclude that time-packing signaling decoded using a LMS transversal filter is an interesting solution to implement the optical feeder link of HTS system, designed to offer global 5G/5G+ connectivity.

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